

ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES (ESP) APPROACH TO LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. This article discusses the general overview and course design of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) in the context of ELT (English Language Teaching). In addition, this article provides a theoretical analysis of the fundamental ideas of ESP, including its definition and function as a learning approach, as well as associated topics like syllabus, learning objectives, materials, methodology, needs analysis—a fundamental component of ESP—and evaluation of ESP-based English language instruction.

Keywords: *method, ESP, ESP syllabus, approach, language, material*

INTRODUCTION

Answering questions like “What is English for a specific purpose?” is difficult because, first and foremost, there must be special courses with specific curricula offered by our universities. Another important point is teacher training, which means that teachers must obtain special training and become more specialised to teach such courses because they are teaching not only English but also special technical terms according to different subjects. More and more colleges throughout the world are offering ESP courses to fulfil the global demand as well as students’ future employment requirements. EGP, the long-standing method of teaching English in many universities, should be replaced with ESP, according to certain higher education administrators and authorities in many countries. This would make ESP the standard for university English instruction.

Therefore, “English for specific purposes is a term that refers to teaching or studying English for a particular career (like law, medicine, journalism or business) in general”. (International Teacher Training Organization, 2005). The fact that “learners know specifically why they are learning a language” (Hutchinson and Waters, 1992) is a great advantage on both sides of the process.

Like any other teaching approach, ESP has advantages and disadvantages. ESP teachers cannot typically draw on personal experiences when assessing materials and thinking about course objectives because they come from backgrounds unrelated to the discipline they are required to teach. Furthermore, they cannot depend on the opinions of students who frequently lack knowledge of the English proficiency needed for the career they intend to pursue. As a result, many ESP teachers end up being enslaved to the available published textbooks, even when such textbooks aren’t quite appropriate for the student’s needs.

Most theorists concur that needs analysis forms the foundation of ESP (Hutchinson and Waters, 1987; Robinson, 1991). Dudley-Evans and St. John (1998) highlight that a significant portion of ESP instruction, particularly that related to a specific profession or discipline, employs a methodology that is different from that of teaching general English. Furthermore, according to Dudley-Evans and St. John (1998) “all ESP teaching should reflect the methodology of the disciplines and professions it serves, and in more specific ESP teaching the nature of the interaction

between the teacher and the learner may be very different from that in a general English class.” These are two more aspects of ESP methodology that the authors emphasize. According to a prominent ELT specialist in Business English, teachers today need to recognize trends like microlearning, personalized learning, on-demand learning, and technology becoming a part of everyday life rather than an add-on. They should also shift the focus from evaluating language learning proficiency to the effectiveness of communication that is achieved in the workplace through the use of English as a lingua franca (Frendo, 2023).

We frequently ask ourselves, “What is the difference between the ESP and “General English” approach?” “In theory nothing, in practice a great deal” is Hutchinson’s straightforward response to this query. Although they acknowledged that students had a stated reason for learning English at the time, instructors of “General English” classes hardly ever carried out a needs analysis to determine what was required to truly accomplish that goal. However, teachers nowadays are far more conscious of the value of needs analysis, and published textbooks have significantly improved, enabling teachers to choose resources that closely align with the learner’s objectives.

ESP characteristics and purpose

English for Specific Purposes and General English share many similarities in terms of how they are taught to meet particular needs and criteria, but they also differ to some degree. General English focuses on the English language in general, unrelated to any particular situation. There is no preference for one language skill over another, whether it be speaking, reading, writing, or listening. Its goal is for the student to reach a level of competency that enables them to interact with native speakers of the language. Furthermore, there is no need for analysis for General English courses. Any course addressing general English would include reading comprehension, vocabulary, grammar, a variety of speaking and listening materials, and any other material on language use. Stated differently, GE’s curriculum is quite conventional. In contrast, ESP courses should ideally have a needs analysis done prior to the course to determine the learners' precise needs and how to address them in a particular curriculum. Occasionally, this is done after the course to gauge student feedback and determine whether the course met its goals and satisfied the students, should it require improvement.

ESP appears to be more complicated for teachers than General English, which is a further consideration. This is usually the result of the instructor having to acquire and study the terminology of a particular profession that he is completely unfamiliar with, or that he may have a general understanding of but not enough to teach. To prepare for any issue in class, the instructor must conduct research for the ESP course and prepare thoroughly. However, the instructor does not need to study before teaching a class in general English because he is an expert in the subject. This is in contrast to the typical preparation for classes.

According to Dudley-Evans and John (1998), ESP has the following qualities and features: Strevens (1998) provides a more thorough definition of ESP, characterizing it as a specific instance of the general category of special-purpose language instruction. Additionally, he disclosed that the concept of ESP must differentiate between two variable and four absolute qualities. English language instruction has four fundamental features:

1. It is tailored to the needs of the students;
2. It is connected to specific disciplines, professions, and activities in terms of content (i.e., themes and topics);

3. It is focused on language which is suitable for those activities in terms of syntax, lexicon, discourse, semantics, etc. and analysis of this discourse;
4. It is differentiated from General English.

According to the definitions provided, ESP is thought to be about educating students to use English in settings where it will be employed, such as academic, professional, or workplace settings. In ESP, learning English is done to facilitate admittance or increase linguistic proficiency in specific contexts rather than for its own sake or to obtain a broad education (Basturkmen, 2006).

Table 1. ESP qualities and features by Dudley-Evans and John

Qualities	Features
it fulfils the learners' specific goals; it makes use of the discipline's underlying methodology and activities; it is centred and focused on language that is appropriate for these activities in terms of grammar, lexis, register, study skills, discourse, and genre.	ESP is related to or designed for specific disciplines; ESP may be used in special teaching contexts or even in a different methodology from general English; ESP is probably intended for adult learners, either in a professional work setting or at a postsecondary institution.

Methods of teaching ESP

The ESP method is extensively used to teach English at secondary and higher levels in Uzbekistan, especially for non-English department students. The goal of teaching English at the University level for non-English department students is to improve their ability to use English for academic and professional purposes, such as reading authentic textbooks. Hutchinson (1998) has underlined how crucial it is to take into account the methodological elements of ESP instruction in order to meet the unique demands of ESP students. To support the problem-solving and task-oriented aspect of communication exercises, five principles have been identified: *information transmission, information gap, jigsaw, task dependency*, and content correction. Effective learning has been found to need consideration of local culture and the atmosphere of the classroom, and one of the main duties of teachers is to choose activities based on those factors (Canagarajah, 2002). Javid (2011) has claimed that because of their varied educational, socioeconomic status, ethnic, and cultural backgrounds, ESP “learners carry differences in their learning styles (LS) as well as diverse language needs”.

Language educators must investigate various teaching methods and techniques in order to adapt them to the unique characteristics of their students and the learning environments. Choosing appropriate pedagogical approaches is inevitable due to the unique and varied personalities of the learners and the learning environments.

With the learner-centred approach known as ESP, each teaching strategy is guided by the unique needs of each student. This approach, which actively involves both ESP practitioners and students, includes needs analysis, development of material and execution, pertinent assessment techniques, etc. Academic and vocational ESP courses are intended for students who wish to use English for academic purposes in a pre-occupational context or for their profession in a post-academic context. It has been determined that learning maturity necessitates that ESP training be delivered not only in classrooms but also through various methods such as *project work, cooperative learning, self-access study*, etc. To effectively conduct an ESP course, ESP practitioners must select from a variety of teaching approaches, as the results of this study clearly

indicate that no single approach can adequately address the many unique needs of ESP learners. Additionally, ESP practitioners must collaborate with content teachers to conduct ESP courses. Because these courses are guided by scientific evaluations of the various individual learner demands, they call for specialized or distinctive techniques.

Initially, a requirements analysis must be carried out before the start of an ESP course. However, what is a requirements analysis and how does one go about doing one? The first step in creating an ESP course that will benefit students in a particular field or circumstance is determining the necessary context.

Next, the language components of that context are analyzed, with the needs of the students being given top priority. That needs analysis could take the kind of an interview, a questionnaire, or both. The interview or questionnaire's components should attempt to relate to the language elements that the course's students need.

ESP curriculum design

When designing an ESP curriculum, there are several key problems. Learners must first acquire the necessary language skills, which are distinct from learning the general language, in order to communicate effectively in professional contexts. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the students' types and whether they are homogeneous or diverse. Additionally, creating content is a very important aspect of creating ESP course curricula. The educational approach and the activities involved in teaching ESP and General English classes are almost the same, despite the fact that those courses have numerous variations, as was previously indicated.

Creating a curriculum for General English courses is easy for instructors because the material topics are consistent and emphasize the four competencies. Topics covered include grammar and practice, reading comprehension, listening, and speaking. Additionally, the same curriculum can be delivered to diverse groups of students. The English language has not evolved throughout time, therefore it can be used for numerous years without alteration. The instructor may update themes, provide new practice tasks, or change the books. Preparing the curriculum for ESP training is vital and mandatory.

Robinson (1991) also proposes two unchangeable standards that identify ESP courses: ESP programs are often goal-oriented, which is the first. Second, they are based on a requirements analysis that will as precisely as possible outline the tasks that the learner must perform in order to speak the language. ESP courses' changeable features imply that the abilities that can be learnt may be limited and that they may not be taught using a certain methodology that is related to or intended for particular fields. Methodologies in specific contexts that differ from standard English may be used in the course.

In order to meet target needs, ESP courses are designed to give students a specific degree of English competence for a scenario in which the language will be utilized. Every choice made while creating language instruction programs in an ESP setting should be based on the needs of the students in terms of learning English. The material of the ESP syllabus should therefore be thoroughly justified in terms of its applicability and capacity to inspire students.

As illustrated in (Taba, H. 1962), Taba divides language syllabus types into three categories: content-based, skills-based, and method-based. The proportionate paradigm represents the first two, while the process paradigm represents the last.

Table 2. Bases for language syllabus design by Taba

Bases for language syllabi					
Content		Skill		Method	
CONTENT Structural focus	TOPIC Informational focus	LANGUAGE Receptive/productive	LEARNING Skill/acquisition focus	PROCESS Learning focus Learner-led	PROCEDURAL Cognitive focus Task-based
SITUATIONAL Structural focus	FUNCTIONAL Notional/functional focus				

The most suitable syllabus type for ESP courses, as suggested by Krahnke, is the content-based syllabus, with the main consideration that it integrates the presentation of topics or tasks from subject matter classes (e.g., Math, Social, Science, etc.) within the context of teaching a second or foreign language. This is because ESP is defined as an approach to language teaching in which students learn the language through the content of subject matters in the field of their specialization for which they learn (Krahnke, 1987, p.65). A syllabus that incorporates many language forms and content integration is known as a content-based syllabus. According to Eskey (1997): It is best to see the content-based syllabus as a more recent attempt to broaden and deepen our understanding of what a second language course syllabus ought to include, including an emphasis on language form and function as well as the third and most important dimension—the factual and conceptual content of such courses.

CONCLUSION

In order to meet its requirements and accomplish fulfilling learning objectives, I paid particular attention to the organization of the ESP course and the selection of the material. I also emphasized the significance and potential methods of evaluation while pointing out some distinctions between the roles of “ESP” and “General English” teachers. I described a goal-oriented method that is focused on the requirements, expectations, and language-learning style of the learners. Since the demands of students must be satisfied more so than those of teachers, and because this depends on the teachers’ attitudes toward the ESP course and their learning tactics, motivation was also highlighted as an essential component of the learning process. In addition, the teacher is responsible for classroom setup and should be knowledgeable about the instructional materials. ESP teachers must be versatile and ready to handle any problems throughout the lesson. Encourage students to create their own resources based on their lesson proposals. To stay up-to-date in the discipline, ESP practitioners should read relevant papers, attend conferences, and seek expert guidance.

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